

Yiguan Dao/I-Kuan Tao 一貫道

By Yong Chen, El Colegio de Mexico

Entry tags: Syncretic Religions, Religious Group, Religious Confucianism

Yiguan Dao/I-Kuan Tao 一貫道 is a salvationist and syncretic religion that originated in the late 19th century in Shandong Province and soon spread throughout other provinces of China. Today it claims to have millions of followers across from Taiwan, Southeast Asia, and many other regions in the world, as well as mainland China where it cannot operate openly. The name Yiguan Dao, meaning the Consistent Way, comes from a phrase by Confucius in the *Analects*, 4:15, "My way has been consistent 吾道一以貫之." Yiguan Dao has demonstrated its effort to evangelize the *sanjiao* tradition, namely, Confucianism, Daoism, and Buddhism, although it is usually poised as the ultimate inheritor of the Five Teachings/Religions (the *sanjiao* plus Christianity and Islam). The origin of Yiguan Dao can be traced back to Luo Jiao, a sectarian religion created by Luo Qing (1442-1527) during the Ming dynasty (1368-1644), which in turn attributed its ancestry to Taiping Dao, a Daoist sect involved in the rebellion of the Yellow Turbans at the end of the Later Han dynasty (25–220). Luo Jiao later evolved into several sects, and one of them was Xiantian Dao, which was suppressed by the Qing government in the early 19th century. In the 1870's, Xiantian Dao further split into several independent sects, one of which later developed into Yiguan Dao (originally named "mohou yizhujiao"—religion for final salvation). The founding of Yiguan Dao with its modern look is generally attributed to Wang Jueyi (1821-1886), who extensively reformed its teachings and rituals in the late 19th century and who is venerated as the 15th patriarch of the tradition. Under the leadership of Zhang Tianran (1889-1947), its 18th patriarch, Yiguan Dao enjoyed rapid growth during the 1930s and 1940s and spread to many provinces of the country. With the establishment of the People's Republic of China in 1949, Yiguan Dao was proscribed an illegal secret society and heretical cult and was eradicated from society as part of the antireligious campaign. At the meantime, however, it grew steadily in Taiwan for decades in spite of the persecution of the Kuomintang government, a policy that was not abolished until 1987. Yiguan Dao embraces an eschatological and soteriological philosophy and presents itself as the only way to salvation. The highest deity worshipped by the followers of Yiguan Dao is called Wusheng Laomu, or the Eternal Venerable Mother, and its worship hall is usually highlighted by the statue of Maitreya Buddha flanked by the statues of the monk Ji Gong and Avalokitesvara (Guan Yin). According to the eschatology and soteriology of Yiguan Dao, human history is divided into three eras: Qingyang Qi or Green Yang Era, Hongyang Qi or Red Yang Era, and Baiyang Qi or White Yang Era. While Dipankara Buddha and Gautama Buddha presided over salvation in the Green Yang Era and the Red Yang Era, respectively, Maitreya Buddha presides over the third period of salvation, the White Yang Era (from 1912 onward). Yiguan Dao practitioners regard the initiation ceremony, called Qiu Dao (seeking the Dao), as the most important ritual, which involves the "offering of the Three Treasures"—the saving grace from the Eternal Venerable Mother. The initiation ceremony articulates the exclusiveness of the membership of Yiguan Dao and only through this ritual can a new member be accepted into the congregation. The members of Yiguan Dao maintain a clear self-identification and call each other Dao Qin (fellows of Dao). Yiguan Dao followers generally believe that the corruption of humanity and natural disasters are associated with the end of the White Yang Era, which ushers in a final salvation. Thus, they emphasize the cultivation of Dao as the opportunity for repentance and purification. This moralizing doctrine paves the way for what scholars have called the "confucianization" of Yiguan Dao, as is clearly seen in its guiding principle: "Respect Heaven and Earth, hold courtesy toward deities; be patriotic to nation and faithful in engagements, cultivate morality and uphold rites; be filial to parents, honor teachers and masters, be trustworthy to friends, be in harmony with neighbors; rectify evil and approach good; be clear with five cardinal relationships and eight virtues." In recent years, Yiguan Dao increasingly draws on Confucian notions to recruit young followers, and the Classics-Recitation Movement (Dujing Yundong) that has swept Taiwan and mainland China in recent decades is largely attributable to the campaign of Yiguan Dao.

Date Range: 1870 CE - 2021 CE

Region: Yiguan Dao in Taiwan

Region tags: Taiwan, Yiguan Dao presence in Taiwan

Yiguan Dao is present throughout Taiwan. This map highlights three cities - Taipei, Taichung, and

Kaohsiung - that feature major Yiguan Dao centres. These are the Tianyuan Treasure Palace (tianyuan bao gong 天元寶宮) in Taipei, the Tianbao Holy Palace (tianbao sheng gong 天寶聖宮) in Taichung, and the Xuanguang Holy Hall (xuanguang sheng tang 玄光聖堂) in Kaohsiung.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Lu Yunfeng. *The Transformation of Yiguan Dao in Taiwan: Adapting to a Changing Religious Economy*. New York: Lexington Books, 2008.
- Source 2: Jochim, Christian. "Popular Lay Sects and Confucianism: A Study Based on the Yiguan Dao in Postwar Taiwan," in *The People and the Dao: New Studies in Chinese Religions in Honour of Daniel L. Overmyer*, ed. by Philip Clart and Paul Crowe, Sankt Augustin: Institut Monumenta Serica, 2009, pp. 83-107.
- Source 3: Soo, Khin Wah. "A Study of the Yiguan Dao (Unity Sect) and Its Development in Peninsular Malaysia." PhD dissertation, University of British Columbia, 1997.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.with.org/>
- Source 1 Description: World Yiguan Dao Headquarters 一貫道世界總會
- Source 2 URL: <https://ikuantao.org.tw/>
- Source 2 Description: Taiwan Yiguan Dao Association 中華民國一貫道總會
- Source 3 URL: <https://tao.org.au/>
- Source 3 Description: Australia Yiguan Dao Headquarters

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.iktcds.edu.tw/Chong-De-School/img/research/201304-11-%E3%80%8C%E4%B8%80%E8%B2%AB%E9%81%93%E3%80%8D%E5%90%8D%E8%A9%9E%E7%BE%A9%E6%B6>
- Source 1 Description: 「一貫道」名詞義涵
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.wikiwand.com/zh-hk/%E4%B8%80%E8%B2%AB%E9%81%93>
- Source 2 Description: 一貫道
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.online88.com/show.aspx?id=1022&cid=178>
- Source 3 Description: 一貫道的發展 - 彌勒書院

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Yiguan Dao practitioners regard the initiation ceremony, called Qiu Dao (seeking the Dao), as the most important ritual, and only through this ritual can a new member be accepted into the congregation.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Traditionally, Yiguan Dao depended on Fuji (planchette writing) for group cohesion, but this controversial ritual was largely renounced during the second half of the 20th century. From the 1980s, Yiguan Dao actively recruited new members from college students in Taiwan, which partially contributed to the so-called "confucianization" of the religion due to its promotion of Dujing (classics recitation).

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: There exists a hierarchy of religious professionals in Yiguan Dao, of which the rank of Dianchuan Shi (Enlightening-Transmitting Master) is probably the most important. Dianchuan Shi, usually designated by the Patriarch (the highest leader), is in charge of the initiation ceremony for the conversion of a new member.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:
– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:
– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The political support from the Taiwan government is often nominal and ceremonial. For example, in 2017, Tsai Ing-wen, President of the Republic of China (Taiwan) participated in the Heaven Worship Ceremony of Yiguan Dao and gave a speech.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 10

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There exists a hierarchy of religious professionals or leaders in Yiguan Dao, of which the highest rank is called Zushi (patriarch). Wang Jueyi (1821-1886), the actual founder of Yiguan Dao, is recognized as the 15th patriarch of the religious genealogy. The last recognized Zushi are Zhang Tianran (1889-1947) and his wife Sun Suzhen (1895-1975).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– I don't know

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– I don't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Zhang Tianran (1889-1947), the 18th patriarch of Yiguan Dao, is believed to be the incarnation of the monk Ji Gong (1130-1209) and have possessed the supernatural powers of

the latter.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: In general, the patriarchs of Yiguan Dao are regarded as infalible, but the interpretations of the teachings often differ. After Yiguan Dao was exiled to Taiwan in 1949, it actually split into two factions, Madame Sun Fraction (Shimu Pai) and Chief Disciple Fraction (Shixiong Pai), as well as sub-fractions.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Occasionally, the religious professionals of Yiguan Dao draw on the scriptures of Buddhism, Daoism, Confucianism, Christianity, and Islam for their teachings. But they more often use two important works written by Zhang Tianran: Yiguandao yiwen jieda (Questions and Answers of Yiguan Dao) and Zanding fogui (Tentative Buddhist Regulations).

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Yiguan Dao uses planchette writing to produce texts and the texts are later compiled into volumes, usually called Shan Shu (Moral Books). The two most important moral books were compiled by Zhang Tianran, called Yiguandao yiwen jieda (Questions and Answers of Yiguan Dao) and Zanding fogui (Tentative Buddhist Regulations).

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

- ↳ Inspired by high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:
 - Yes
- ↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Originated from non-divine human being:
 - Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

- Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

- No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

- No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The religious architecture of Yiguan Dao is called Fotang (Buddhist Hall). There are four types of religious architecture present: family Fotang, public Fotang, central Fotang, and Daochang (Grand Hall of Dao).

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

- I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

- I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

- I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 200

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Family hall or altar

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Zhang Tianran, the 18th Patriarch, is believed to be the incarnation of the monk Ji Gong (1130-1209).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Yiguan Dao worships the Eternal Venerable Mother (Wusheng Laomu), also called the Infinite Mother (Wujimu). It is neither male nor female, though it is called "Mother" or "Heavenly Mater". It is the primordial force of the universe, the source of all things.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample

region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: the moral wellbeing of humanity

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: For example, Zhang Tianran, the 18th Patriarch, is believed to be the reincarnation of the monk Ji Gong (1130-1209).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - I don't know

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes

- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes

Notes: The presence of non-human supernatural beings is ambiguous in the teachings of Yiguan Dao. The followers generally believe that the Eternal Venerable Mother gave birth to yin and yang (two ontological and spiritual principles) and two children, Fuxi and Nüwa (two mythological figures), who begot auspicious stars and all sentient beings.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: the future of human destiny
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes

- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Food:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sacred space(s):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– No

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:
– No

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Yiguan Dao centers on the Maitreya belief, which is millenarian and which claims that the world

would come to an end soon and Maitreya (a Buddha) would incarnate himself in the physical plane to save humanity.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
– Yes

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Yiguan Dao followers believe that the human beings were sent to the east and lost their memory of the Eternal Venerable Mother, thus the corruption of the Dao. The Mother sent to the material world three enlightened beings over the "Three Eras": the Green Yang Era, the Red Yang Era, and the White Yang Era. Dipankara Buddha presided over salvation in the Green Yang Era, Gautama Buddha in the Red Yang Era, and Maitreya Buddha will preside over the third period of salvation, the White Yang Era, which began in 1912 and continues even now.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:
– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:
– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
– Yes

↳ Divine judgment event:
– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:
– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: seek the Dao

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The moral code of Yiguan Dao is primarily Confucian, which can be seen clearly in its guiding principle: “Respect Heaven and Earth, hold courtesy toward deities; be patriotic to nation and faithful in engagements, cultivate morality and uphold rites; be filial to parents, honor teachers and masters, be trustworthy to friends, be in harmony with neighbors; rectify evil and approach good; be clear with five cardinal relationships and eight virtues.”

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– Only specialized religious class

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):
– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes

- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: propriety

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

- No
- I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

- No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

- No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

- No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

- No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

- No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

- No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

- No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

- No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

- No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

- No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: With permission from the religious authority, the vegetarian Daoqin (fellows of Dao), more strict in following the moral code, can set up family halls or altars at their homes to conduct religious services.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: There are four types of religious architecture in Yiguan Dao: family Fotang, public Fotang, central Fotang, and Daochang (Grand Hall of Dao). The latter three Fotangs are for large-scale rituals and religious activities.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 50

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Yiguan Dao was especially well-known for its famine relief activities during the Japanese invasion of China during 1937-1945.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: This is my impression. They are deeply committed to social causes.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: They have created two colleges, I-Kuan Tao College and I-Kuan Tao Chongde College, to provide higher education to their adherents. There is also an elementary school in Pingdong county affiliated with Yiguan Dao.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a hierarch of religious professionals within the religion and religious authority is extensively involved in religious activities.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No